

Summary results of Tarn-et-Garonne case study (CS2)

Policy Brief

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H2020-LC-GD-2020-2: LC-GD-9-2-2020. Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation

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Rethinking Tarn-et-Garonne region in a changing climate

Key findings

- Stakeholder engagement: Co-design ensures solutions are relevant, feasible, and accepted locally.
- Climate risks: Increased rainfall variability, occasional droughts, and extreme storms threaten crop production, water availability, and tourism.
- Land-based adaptation & mitigation: Agroforestry, cover crops, and reduced tillage can reduce climate risks and support sustainable agriculture.
- Water management: Efficient retention, irrigation optimization, and watershed management are critical to cope with droughts and heavy rainfall.
- Forests & landscapes: Protecting and restoring forested areas supports timber production, tourism, and landscape value.
- Energy readiness: Developing infrastructure and training for renewable energy strengthens local energy autonomy.
- Policy integration: Early stakeholder consultation helps identify barriers and ensure successful LAMS implementation.

Keywords: Tarn-et-Garonne; land-use; LAMS; water security; energy; adaptation; mitigation, climate resilience

Executive Summary

Tarn-et-Garonne, located in the South-West of France within the Occitanie region, covers 3,717 km² and has a population of 262,316. The climate is warm, with nearly 2,000 hours of sunshine per year. Landscapes vary from plains along the Tarn, Garonne, and Aveyron rivers to hills reaching 510 meters in the north and south-west. The department's economy relies heavily on agriculture (fruits, cereals, vineyards), nature-based tourism, and local energy systems. Agriculture covers about 72% of land use and employs roughly 5% of the population. Many farms depend on irrigation, which affects over a quarter of the utilised agricultural area. Forests cover around 24% of the territory, mainly privately owned for timber production. This policy brief distils stakeholder-selected **land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS)** that support sustainable land management, and strengthen climate resilience. It outlines practical options to enhance water security, promote climate-smart farming, and support renewable energy development. The brief is intended for regional policymakers, local authorities, farmer cooperatives, tourism operators, and energy planners.

Source: <https://pixabay.com/>

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Background & Policy Context

Climate change acts as a risk multiplier, intensifying existing challenges through interactions between climatic and non-climatic drivers, such as land-use change. In Tarn-et-Garonne, changes in agricultural practices, urbanization, and landscape management influence local climate resilience and the potential for decarbonisation. Achieving sustainable land management and climate neutrality in line with the European Union (EU) Green Deal objectives for 2050 ([Chiriaco et al., 2025](#)¹) requires coordinated action at the regional level.

The RethinkAction project supports these objectives by co-developing land-use-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) with local stakeholders in six EU case studies, including Tarn-et-Garonne, aiming to reduce land-use-based emissions and enhance climate resilience across different land-use types.

¹ Chiriaco, M.V. et al. (2025). A catalogue of land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions to tackle climate change. *Sci Data* 12, 166 [[doi](#)].

High-resolution land use maps of *Tarn-et-Garonne* region. Source: RethinkAction project

Tarn-et-Garonne is one of the six RethinkAction case studies exploring different land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) to support the EU Green Deal objectives.

The department’s economy relies heavily on agriculture (fruits, cereals, vineyards), nature-based tourism, and local energy systems. Policies need to balance economic development with sustainable land management, while promoting optimal water management and building climate resilience.

Air temperature for scenario SSP5-8.5 and period 2041-2070. Source: *RethinkAction Platform*

Climate & Geographic Focus for LAMS

Influenced by the Mediterranean and Atlantic climate patterns, Tarn-et-Garonne has a warm temperate climate with nearly 2,000 hours of sunshine per year. Summers are hot and dry, while winters are mild with moderate rainfall, mainly concentrated in spring and autumn.

Agricultural systems rely partly on rainfall but are also highly dependent on irrigation, particularly for fruit orchards, cereals, and vineyards. Localized water stress can occur during dry periods, and increased water demand during the tourism high season can put pressure on water supply systems. The department has moderate wind potential and good solar resources, offering opportunities for the development of renewable energy.

Land-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) were co-designed with stakeholders and are central to ensuring that Tarn-et-Garonne remains productive, climate-resilient, and sustainable.

Bridging Science and Society for Climate-Resilience Development

RethinkAction used state-of-the-art tools to connect climate scenarios with land-use decisions and policy options. The applied methodology combined climate modelling, land-use analysis, stakeholder engagement, and System Dynamics modelling to co-design actionable pathways. A participatory, multi-scale approach was applied, combining quantitative modelling with multiple stakeholder co-creation workshops across six case studies to evaluate different future alternatives.

Data collection, modelling, and policy analysis were implemented. A total of five basic Essential Climate Variables (Basic-ECVs) and 24 Derived-ECVs were downscaled to assess future exposures, followed by the identification of suitable LAMS based on the literature review and multicriteria analysis and their suitability at the local scale. In addition, crop yield anomalies were analysed in AquaCrop to assess the future crop yields and climate change conditions. Local stakeholders were involved in the evaluation of the potential risks across sectors through impact chains and the selection of potential packages of solutions, along with the main potential drivers and barriers.

For essential climate variables, Aquacrop, risk quantification and local system dynamic model, the RethinkAction project used Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) were SSP1-2.6 (with lower emissions), SSP2-4.5 (with mid-range emissions)

Translating Data into Action

Tarn-et-Garonne is already experiencing more frequent late frosts, summer heat extremes, and water stress in orchards. Extreme rainfall events are also growing in frequency, increasing risks of flooding. There is no strong literature yet showing hail becoming more regular in T-et-G, but farmers are concerned about damage from hail in fruit-producing areas.

Temperatures expected to increase up to +8°C by 2100 under SSP5-8.5. **Temperature** is a **critical indicator** that will strongly influence the province’s **future water availability** with cascading effects on communities and several climate-sensitive sectors.

Mean wind speeds seems not to change or could slightly decline by the end of the century, potentially affecting wind power production.

Number of dry days may increase by 20 days by 2100 with SSP5-8.5. Total rainfall is not planned to change rather its repartition throughout the year. Higher temperatures also drive-up cooling demand, increasing thermal stress for both people and ecosystems.

Local workshop three in T&G (January 2024).
Source: RethinkAction project.

Anomalies of the mean temperature for T&T comparing the period 2071-2100 to the historical period (1985 - 2015) for SSP 5.8.5. Source: RethinkAction project.

AquaCrop results show a significant decrease in maize up to 47% than the current yield. For potato and apple, it is projected relatively low differences in the future.

This information was fed into the simulation of the local system dynamics model, which can be used in the RethinkAction platform to test the policies and trade-offs. The results highlight that sustainable water management is the most urgent challenge, requiring efficient irrigation, improved storage, ecosystem restoration, and public awareness. Agroecological transition, such as crop diversification, cover crops, agroforestry, and compost use, offer resilience, support carbon sequestration, and open opportunities for circular economy and carbon credits, though financial and regulatory frameworks are key. Beyond agriculture, rural tourism and renewable energy are also vulnerable and call for integrated land-use planning to balance synergies and trade-offs.

Quantified risk through Impact Chains in Tarn-et-Garonne for agriculture sector. Source: RethinkAction project

Considering the most relevant risks, stakeholders had chosen specific LAMS for water management and agriculture sectors. The LAMS displayed are “Improved water use efficiency: agriculture, domestic, industry”, “Increase use of treated wastewater” and “Regenerative agriculture”.

Local SD Model – Simulation Results

Water demand in Tarn-et-Garonne, under low, medium and high level of implementation intensity, for SSP1 scenario.

Source: RethinkAction project.

Stakeholder-Chosen LAMS

Water use efficiency: agriculture, domestic industry

Increase use of treated wastewater

Regenerative agriculture

Conclusions

The Tarn-et-Garonne must respond to climate risks with measures that balance economic activity and ecosystem protection. Building resilience requires improving water-use efficiency, protecting natural land and expanding solar energy. However, implementation of these measures requires assessment of the drivers and barriers, along with stakeholder participation. Without such alignment, the expected goals cannot be achieved. Active local engagement, coherent policies can secure food security, safeguard natural assets, and ensure a reliable energy transition for future generations. The key outcomes described in this document are available in the Resources section of the [RethinkAction website](#) and in the [RethinkAction platform](#).

² Barilari, S. et al. (2025). Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment in the Province of Almeria (Spain) Under Different Climate Change Scenarios. *Climate*, 13(7), 141. [\[doi\]](#).

Impact chains were used to analyse these complex vulnerable conditions, considering all the factors involved. They are a tool that considers all the risk components and synthesizes the complex connections between them. They were quantified in the project following ([Barilari et al., 2025²](#)) and the results are available in the [RethinkAction platform](#).

Two **Impact Chains** were developed to define the risks in this case study: Risk of decreased water quality and availability affecting yields of tree crops; Risk of negative impact on water quality and quantity due to human activities.

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